

Emotional and Ingenious Marketing Campaigns for successful Brand promotions: A Case Study Based Approach on Indian Marketers

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ABSTRACT

Indians are emotion centric people and marketers understood this. Marketers have been using emotional appeal in their marketing campaigns to connect with the Indian consumers for long. They gauged it as the best tool to place their brands strategically in the minds of the people. The new breed of advertisements touches the strong issues which are prevalent in our society and try to break the traditional norms, improve the country's values, attitude, lifestyle, and thoughts, thus make Indians question the current situation. Companies in most cases keep their brand presence in these campaigns minimal but indulge in storytelling to captivate their audience. Thoughts which reiterated the importance of innovative and social marketing campaigns to Indian marketers are taken into consideration. This paper is a case study-based approach to focus on some of the major campaigns which influenced the Indian society. The cases are used as a basis to compare the various strategic campaigns of different marketers, why they thought their campaign to be emotional, effective, and innovative and how it helped them to maintain sustainability. The personal observations of the author lend a unique perspective as to how the growing importance of strategic brand promotions and management and undertaking of innovative marketing campaigns by Indian marketers influenced the common people thought process.

This paper traces the evolution and importance of strategic brand promotions management through innovative marketing campaigns in India. It projects the current state of the field and offers an insight into how Indian marketers have successfully used digital, social media platforms and real physical locations to conduct innovative and social marketing campaigns. Brands like Lifebuoy, BIBA, etc. undertook various such projects for the social good. However, this paper tries to bring light on companies like Mankind Pharma, ZEE Entertainment, Hyundai, British Airways and analyze them.

Key words: Innovative Marketing Campaigns, Social Marketing, Emotional Appeal, Influencer marketing, Strategic Brand Management

INTRODUCTION

Innovative and creative marketing campaigns has been the key to forming brand value. Innovation in the selection of appeal and the means of communicating the marketing message have changed dramatically in the recent years. The companies are focusing on linking brands with socially responsible attributes and are successful in portraying the brand values that are ethical and social, alongside the mission and vision of the company.

The advertisements and marketing campaigns which are being launched by these companies carry a social message. These social messages include the intrinsic and extrinsic problems of the society. Some of the marketing campaigns aim at changing the traditional norms. These archaic traditions and rituals are embedded deep into the social fabric. Some marketing campaigns focus on the problems of the modern society and the issues related to the urban areas. The ways of addressing these issues of the urban and rural India is by using emotional appeal. Indians by nature are emotional and sentimental. Marketers have identified it and have been using this to their benefit. Emotional advertising appeal has a significant influence on brand attitude. Thus, it is important for the marketers to use emotional appeal in their marketing campaigns. There has also been an increase in the use of altruism appeal. Altruism appeal is the use of marketing tools and resources to promote causes for wellbeing of the society, and the marketing campaign is not focused on the profit generation for the company.

For keeping the company salient to the consumers, the marketers are using social issues and emotional appeal. This helps in increasing the perceived brand value to the customer and thereby increase the brand franchise and brand equity. Brand management includes identifying the areas where the brand can focus to introducing new ideas, planning the marketing strategy and subsequent evaluation of brand performance due to the new creative advertising techniques. The focus is on providing value to the customers.

The importance of brand management in VUCA environment is even more important. VUCA stands for Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity and Ambiguity. The term VUCA was coined by the American Military in the ending phase of Cold War. Its relation to the business can be conceptualised as business world is very hostile and there is confusion, uncertainty, and difficulty throughout. The primary objective of a company should be to identify its weaknesses and strengthening it. The other things the marketer should be aware of is to be conscious about its consumer behaviour and trends and the things the customers are more susceptible to. Branding is very important in the VUCA environment as there is cutthroat competition in the market and everyone is busy finding ways to woo the customers. A good strategy would be to link the goals and attributes of an organisation to social causes and emotions as it is the most effective way to form a positive attitude towards the brand by the customers. The marketer has to be proactive in identifying the problem and issues faced by its customers, and solving them before others do, and promote the initiative in a way which does not hurt the sentiments of the people. Business is a war and surviving it is much more difficult than entering it. Ninety percent of the businesses shut down within the first three years. It is imperative to strategize the product according to the needs of the customers and stimulating the customers with the right type of marketing mix.

Sustainability:

Sustainability in marketing means use of tools of marketing which promote long term value addition to the brand image, increment in brand equity and formation of brand franchise. Brand image is the positive attitude towards the brand by the customers. Brand equity is the total value of the brand. Sustainability is a process, and it is hard earned. For a brand to be sustainable and to be able to survive the long haul, it should have a set of brand values which are in line with the customers' intrinsic values, it should review its brand value and objectives on a regular basis and should work in improving it continuously. The brand should form an emotional relationship with the customers so that the customers are able to identify themselves with the brand.

Forming a bond with the customers is the most important aspect of brand building. The company should use ethical marketing tools. Marketer should also focus on brand retention in the minds of the customers and brand recall so that they can associate the brand with the product. When the perceived risk of the customer relating to the marketer is less, then he is more inclined towards associating himself with the brand. The marketer must build trust with better value proposition for the customers, better customer relation and honest marketing communication.

Using a strong functional issue and/or linking it with an emotional aspect using integrated marketing communication, which involves different dimensions of marketing mix, promotion and customer relationship management programs can build a trust in the minds of the customer for the brand. Sometimes the marketing mix used by the marketer focuses more on the functional issue and the solution to it, and in the process the branding aspect takes a back seat. The brand is barely visible in the advertisement in such cases. This type of marketing is done mainly to address the problems of the customers and the social issues relating to them. The brand remains subliminally present which is faintly but certainly recognised by the customers. Subliminal branding, though being minimalistic in nature, does have a positive impact on buying behaviour of the customers (Sofi and Nika, 2013).

The effect of these indirect, subliminal advertisement with altruism appeal might not have a fast outcome with sharp rise in sales of the brand, but the brand equity created is more valuable. A positive brand perception stays in the minds of the customers which increases the trust in the brand. In the long term, these attributes provide better competitive advantage in the market which is very important for the survival of the brand for a longer time.

Change in buying behavior

Advertising messages aim at influencing consumer behavior, product attitudes, and even purchase intentions (Belch and Belch, 1998). Consumers get attracted and show interest in buying the product due to the communication of advertising message. The brand recall and brand attitude are positive in case of marketers who try to do something different, leaving an impact in the consumer's minds. The consumers of today are not only interested in product attributes, but they also care deeply about value proposition of the brands. This is exactly the scenario in today's world where nothing is certain and market dynamics are always changing.

Change in psychology of the modern customers

Today's advertisements reflect the problems and issues the society faces. Through these social marketing campaigns, the marketers are trying to bring out the solutions to those problems and it is attracting the modern consumers. The marketers are aiming to place their brands strategically, often subliminally but positively.

Objectives:

Innovativeness in the marketing campaigns is the only avenue through which marketers can strategically place their brands in the consumer's minds. In today's world, marketers have to think about long term sustainability which is helped through positioning their companies acting in an innovative, socially responsible and "different" way.

1. To study the innovative campaigns undertaken by four different companies in four different fields
2. To analyze how they strategically managed their brands through the social connect of their campaign

The innovative marketing campaigns ensures two-way communication between the company and target audience. The feedback from them paves the way for increasing trust and mutual dependency between the two sides. In a VUCA world, the best way for business sustainability in the long run is through nurturing this precious relationship. This paper tries to focus on the societal implications and the relationship goals the companies and marketers achieved by strategically engaging their brands in these innovative marketing campaigns

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Kotler and Zaltman (1971) discussed how social marketing can be used as an avenue of planned social change. They tried to evaluate whether the marketing concepts and techniques of commercial products can be effectively used to inculcate social objectives like safe driving and family planning. They told according to Wiebe in 1952, the chances of a social campaign being successful is directly proportional to its resemblance to a product campaign. They vouched social marketing to be a promising framework for planning and implementing social change but poorly understood and thus restrained. They felt the application of conventional marketing ideas in achieving social goals was not encouraged at that time.

2. Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) discussed the relationship between attitude and the influence it has on social behavior. They wrote how we can understand, define and measure behavior and also how intention is a major determinant of behavior. They explained the attitude behavior correspondence in predicting and understanding family planning behaviors and the beliefs, attitudes and intentions associated with it. They talked about women's occupational orientations – with specific importance on the factors underline choice intentions. The determinants of the attitudinal and normative components were also discussed at length. To build their case, they used the examples of American elections, British elections, and American referenda. They also illustrated the theory's general application via change in the behavior of alcoholics.

3. Batra and Ray (1986), in their paper talked about affective responses (ARs). They discussed how the list of cognitive responses have expanded slowly to take in the customer acceptance. They argued ARs should be also taken under the scope of communication research along with cognitive responses. The moods and feelings which are evoked through the advertisements in the customer's minds are because of such, and not necessarily evaluative responses to an advertisement. They reviewed the literature on AR available and came up with a typology for such responses. They empirically studied three ARs and they appeared to be antecedents of the attitudes towards the ads and to have a weak but significant impact on brand attitude.

4. Belch and Belch (2003) wrote in their book about the change in 'advertising and promotion' segment of marketing. They talked how marketers transcended beyond traditional media for success. To facilitate communication with consumers they talked about integrating the tools of marketing like advertising, public relations, direct marketing, internet marketing, sales promotion, and personal selling. IMC was first talked about in this and underlined the importance of presenting a unified message to the consumer from the company through all available channels.

5. Berger and Schwartz (2011) talked about the factors driving immediate and ongoing word of mouth. They correctly observed different products have different word of mouth experiences both after immediate consumer launch and also later in the product cycle. They tried to ascertain the psychological drivers of the same. It was an unique empirical study of everyday conversations for more than three hundred products simultaneously across the field (various cities) and also in a controlled laboratory environment. They analyzed more interesting products may get more immediate attention but may not receive the same over multiple months but products that are cued more by the environment or are easily accessible to the public receive more WOM both right away and over time.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The proposed case study has been done through an Exploratory Research Design with only secondary data. The main focus of this study was to do a case study-based understanding of the strategic and innovative marketing campaigns. The author is trying to make this paper to serve as a tool for initial research that provides a hypothetical or theoretical idea of the research problem. This qualitative research was dived deep into 4 different advertising campaigns and tried to understand the social connect. Thus, it may be termed as a meta-analysis of the literature review.

CASES

Prega News #OfficeIsYourSecondHome Campaign

Introduction:

The campaign “OFFICE IS YOUR SECOND HOME” from Prega News (Mankind Pharmaceuticals) is a socially relevant and challenging concept in today’s world. Created by ADK Fortune, the campaign urges corporate houses to treat pregnant employees as their own family members and cherish their journey. It is a masterpiece of storytelling concept by Indian Marketers which reaches the heart of millions. The advertisement featured and aimed at pregnant working women and corporate houses and develops an intricate, heartwarming, and positive storyline. The digital film with a unique reach towards trust and relationships grabbed attention and become a topic of discussion on social media instantly after it was introduced on Mother’s Day. It was a brilliant strategic campaign which instantly won over PregaNews’s main consumer base- expecting women. PregaNews’s role did not complete their presence just after confirming “The Good News”, but became a companion.

Narration:

The film starts with two corporate managers. One is really agitated with this year’s results and wants to reduce employee costs. But the other manager is lost deep in thought and not really participating in the conversation. He calls out to the peon of the office asking about the belongings of Shweta Ma’am (a female employee) and whether he had packed them yet. The peon reassured the boss that he has already done that and is a bit surprised on being ordered to bring water and food to meetings on a regular basis from then. The film reveals a certain secret mission like thing going on in the office- someone lovely clearing Shweta’s cubicle, all her belongings, the designing of a special cabin with comfortable chairs and no smell chimneys are installed. The next day, viewers catch the first glimpse of Shweta- a smiling, lovely girl greeting everyone in the office en route her cubicle. But on reaching there she is shocked to see it cleared and is anxious when a colleague calls out to her to go and talk with the H.R. She is devastated and blames her boss in her mind thinking she is fired because she is pregnant! While going to the H.R. department, she discovers her nameplate hanging outside a spacious cabin. When she steps inside, she observes the cabin has been designed especially according to her maternal needs and comfort. She is delighted and her superior entered sharing her “Good News”. According to him, “Becoming a mother isn’t easy and we are making less difficult for you. After all office is your second home!” Shweta is touched by this act of kindness and understanding. While departing, her boss reminds her of the client meeting and Shweta’s smile shows the viewers she is enough strong to take both the responsibilities- a working woman and a mother! She is happy, sated, content in her new life and surroundings! This three-minute 27 seconds advertisement strikes a chord instantly. It sensitizes towards the working pregnant women and the issues they face in their workplaces.

The Innovative Idea and Brand Management through Social Connect:

Pregnancy is a beautiful phase of life but full of challenges, all-the-more for a working woman. This campaign pays tribute to women who continue to work throughout their pregnancy. The digital film highlights the issues working pregnant mothers face at their workplace. Since they spend most of their time in offices (basically more than a third of the day), the responsibility of making their lives comfortable during this phase falls on the companies, according to the brand. The campaign tries to iterate how companies lose talent due to uncomfortable workplace conditions during pregnancy and how thoughtful gestures can mitigate the problem. PregaNews is requesting corporate companies to be more sensitive to a pregnant woman’s needs according to the new Maternity Benefit (Amendment) Act. Last year, Bollywood royalty Kareena Kapoor became the ambassador of the brand when she was pregnant. In the Indian society, pregnant women are expected to sit at home. But the recent trends show many women continue to work despite being pregnant and it is indeed a praiseworthy step! Prega News urges the companies to customize their work culture and surroundings to support this cause. After all, “A Mother is a Hero and should be applauded!” Prega News has just not only made this video as a part of this campaign but is trying to engage the consumers with more communication. The brand’s website is offering consultative services for offices on how they can make their work culture and decor pregnancy friendly. A micro site has been created to urge more people to support the cause and make people more aware. Some time back, the brand partnered with SpiceJet Airways to launch a series of initiatives to make air travel for pregnant women more comfortable and enjoyable. This was an extension to the “YourSecondHome” and resonated extremely well with all the expectant mothers.

The brand reiterates the feeling that every sphere of a woman’s life should make her cherished during her special phase, including her office- which is her second home- spending more than a third of her day there! The advertisement has a positive vibe throughout and may encourage working expectant mothers to continue living their dream! The campaign focuses on social good- the use of Altruism Appeal is noteworthy. It works like a Multiplier Effect in this campaign, a small kindness and support on part of the employer will be remembered by the employees forever. Throughout the film, the brand is not mentioned at all until the rolling credits where the brand shares the “Good News”. This campaign started in Pre COVID times. It is still significant in 2021, when COVID is going down and companies are looking at re-opening offices- women empowerment and making special facilities for working women continue to being a major objective.

ZEE #ArmybehindtheArmy Campaign

Introduction:

Indian Army is the reason Indians sleep peacefully at night. They are our source of peace, contentment, and guardians of our safety. But how do they derive their strength? Who gives them so much courage to battle against every odd and be victorious? How do they manage to be so bold and sure in their work? The truth is their strength is made up with another army of their families- their mothers, wives, sisters, daughters who with a brave heart and smiling face work day and night playing the roles of their sons, husbands, brothers and fathers who are dutifully saving the nation. Zee Entertainment Enterprises has created an ode to their true heroism by their campaign #ArmybehindtheArmy.

#ArmyBehindTheArmy has been created and conceptualized by Zee's creative agency - FCB Ulka Advertising.

Zee sings the laurel for this true army not with gun salutes, medals, and honour - but with respect, love and care. They recognize the true worth of their sacrifice. The campaign evolved around and had a regal culmination on Republic Day. The campaign brought tears to anyone who watched- but did not portray the women as helpless- rather they have replaced that and become the true leaders of their world. The whole of India related with and hailed this campaign to be socially relevant, strategically placed and needed for empowering women.

Narration:

The salutation anthem film of Zee "ArmybehindtheArmy" is directed by Ken Rolston from Story Tellers, a leading film production house. The film portrays magically the resolution and inner struggle of these women through a powerful and emotional narrative – Hum Hain. It is a kaleidoscopic montage of portraits of real wives, widows, and mothers of the forces. The women in the families of the soldiers are heroes in themselves. They do the manual labour like agriculture, take care of the kids, do all the household manly work- like fixing a bulb or getting things from a high rack themselves. It is them who advises the engineer regarding their dream home, who takes important decisions for the families, stays vigilant in the hospitals all night for family members. They have only one source of inspiration- the pictures of the men they have sent to the battlefield- in the family albums, who may return to them alive or come back in the coffin wrapped in National Flag. It takes enormous grit and confidence and bravery to fight for life, alone and not give up. They breathe strong, they are the storm. They are self-sufficient to take care of their families and be strong enough emotionally to send their precious men to death's door, being called by duty and sense of honour. It is the ultimate tribute to women empowerment and acknowledging their true strength.

The strong visual cue – a unique visual identity designed by FCB Ulka for the initiative – is inspired by army fatigues, with a camouflage design that is derived from women in various acts of nurturing and caring. This lends a strong visual and emotional character to the communication.

The Innovative Idea and Brand Management through Social Connect:

To any countrymen, national army is something they all look up to, respect and honor. Zee Entertainment by portraying the "Behind Scene" campaign of the Indian Army- the true source of their courage and strength had a great strategic alignment for their brand. Zee Entertainment Enterprises is a global content company which has always focused on Women Empowerment, either through its content offerings or social initiatives. The portraying of the selfless and brave women, who are as strong contenders of Paramvirs and Mahavirs as the actual army people adds more value to their brand image. People connect with their good corporate citizen style. Transcending beyond a mere advertising idea, this initiative is rooted in real life and aims to give army wives and mothers the honor and respect they truly deserve for their role in nurturing families, building strong communities and a healthy nation. It also brings to light the epic work which this real army behind the brave soldiers does, to support its families. For the past 25 plus years, Zee has supported and given Indian women a voice onscreen through its content as well as sought betterment for them through social initiatives. #ArmyBehindTheArmy is another major step taken by Zee in this direction. Zee went beyond the male shadowed concepts of soldier and patriotism and gave it a gender unbiased angle. Army is not only strong men, gunshots, and blood- army is about courage to face difficulties, work against odds and emerge as winners. The brand had minimalistic presence until at the end of the film- where they create the logo of Zee with the montage of women and ends with "Hum Hain". The emotional appeal used here does evoke tears but also strong determination- the true Altruism effect which they wanted to give. Zee backed up this campaign through mass and social media and leading channels of Zee. They undertook various on ground activities and wanted this campaign to have a lasting effect- thus strategically placing their brand too.

Hyundai #Be the Better Guy Campaign

Introduction:

With the staggering increase in road accidents all over India in recent years, all car manufacturing companies were trying to educate and aware their customers on Road Safety issues. Perhaps the most successful, heart-warming and societal approach was by Hyundai through their #BeTheBetterGuy campaign. It was conceptualized by Innocean, who made a terrific mixture of celebrity endorsement and daily life situations to connect with the end consumers. The South Korean company executed a brilliant and strategic brand management operation where they accentuated their brand presence and product throughout the socially responsible campaign- to add to the weight and help the actual drivers connect. The online campaign wanted to make a positive impact and inspire people to adhere to

traffic rules. They draw attention to critical issues pertaining to road safety such as– Underage Driving, Don't Drink & Drive, Usage of Mobile Phone, Over Speeding & Violation of Traffic Signal. The campaign is supported by Ministry of Road Transport and Highways aiming to create a mass movement in India.

Narration:

Hyundai Motor Group's basic CSR initiative around the world has been Safe Move. Throughout the campaign, Hyundai has requested drivers to fight the odds in various adverse situations and "Be the Better Guy". This innovative content has presented Hyundai with a wonderful leverage-playing the role as of a mentor and conscience guide of its customers.

The film begins with the driver taking responsibility for their individual actions. Whenever drivers display responsible behaviour, it must be at the cost of something- either their promotion or losing the tag of "Cool Dad" to their son or keeping loved ones waiting. They had not received laurels for their effort of adherence to the traffic rules. Being the unsung heroes on the roads - they are the Better Guys and Hyundai odes them so that they can positively influence Behaviour Change among others. Hyundai has banked on the star power of its celebrity endorser, Shahrukh Khan, moving him into a more corporate spokesperson role, and portrayed him as the Conscience of the drivers.

The campaign has taken into consideration various everyday situations where a bit of effort on part of drivers can avoid accidents. The campaign reiterates again and again – "Your Car has everything for your safety. Because we (Hyundai) care about you. But do you care about yourself? ... Be The Better Guy!" The ease of narration in the campaign where the drivers trying their best to drive responsibly end up losing something in their lives, Shahrukh Khan reassures them, "It is not necessary you become known for your goodness. Rather it is more advisable to carry on that goodness for a longer period." The human relations were captured brilliantly throughout the campaign- the father-son, sister-brother, husband-wife, boss-employee scenes leave the viewers totally connected with the campaign- because these things happen in our daily lives!

The Innovative Idea and Brand Management through Social Connect:

Hyundai wanted to make people aware that most accidents occur due to behavioural issues and even though every car is loaded with safety features, the main one is inside the driver's head. They are trying their best to switch it on. Responsible people can also be heroes- the campaign portrays. The campaign was available only in digital media for a few reasons. Obviously 30 seconds TVC would not have captured the full message. Rather than having a disparate and sporadic effort, Hyundai wanted to streamline their effort. Secondly India's young adult generation has an impressive percentage of vehicle ownership who are most accustomed to digital platforms; and constant access to devices strengthened the message impact. Another thing Hyundai management had in mind was the role of the young as a positive influence on an older generation- like the father who decreased the speed of the car after the seemingly innocent question from the child. Here, Hyundai wanted them to realize the horror of accidents when a family's future is travelling with them.

Being the advocate of safe driving throughout, Hyundai wants to strategically place their brand in the minds of the consumers as a "Caring Brand". They want to focus on the idea of safe and responsible driving giving birth to a positive behaviour change. Hyundai is confident after the campaign's resounding ongoing success for the last year, it will become a Social Movement with people's participation for a better future. The appeals used are mainly Rational and Altruism- good for everyone by doing your own good.

British Airways #Fuelled By Love Campaign

Introduction:

Airlines are always a special thing for Indians and premium flights- a fairytale treat. British Airways- seeking to increase their customer base in India and looking for a strategic placement of their brand pointed exactly that. An emotion laden campaign, with a storybook drama appeal enabled British Airways to exactly land their flight in the hearts of Indian customers. This campaign #FuelledByLove explains there is no substitute for love and empathy even in specialized care-oriented services like airlines- where professional attitude gives over to heartfelt warmth and care, given the effort of the participants. Conceptualized by SapientNitro, this long format digital film gained enormous popularity across India. The film tells the story of a young cabin crew of British Airways, from U.K. who becomes emotionally involved with one of the elderly passenger women on her maiden trip to India. This campaign was in extension of British Airways previous initiatives like- "A Ticket to Visit Mum", "Go Further to Get Closer", "Wings of Hope" and many others through which has helped them strategically establish their humane brand image. This campaign is no exception, and the brand has a fantastic presence in the inflight sequence of the film- subtly reminding consumers about the brand throughout. The campaign was directed by Neeraj Ghaywann and was introduced on British Airway's official website. It ran alongside on the company's social media channels, and through print, digital, outdoor media campaigns in three until the end of the month. The intensification on social media involved real-life, British Airways' crew stories through short videos and photo essays.

Narration:

Generally, airline advertisements were always told from the viewpoint of travelers, But #Fuelled By Love was an exception because it revolved around the experiences and feelings of the cabin crew. The elderly woman wins over

the heart of the cabin crew and caring for her during the flight was not out of duty but love. The film and its communication work from a differentiated perspective. For instance, it presents India to a western audience and corrects a lot of perceptions, and showcasing the cultural differences, and the warm hospitality of the Indians towards foreigners. British Airways has a rich heritage of over 90 years in India and speaks of deep understanding of this wonderful country. Through this film and the brand campaign, they highlighted upon the actual experiences of their cabin crew members socializing and connecting with Indian passengers. British Airways delivers to the viewers the perfect concoction of love and care and professional service of their cabin crew members through it. The campaign portrays the convergence of two cultures. It is a nice mix of simple acts of goodness, cultural nuances, and subtle display of emotions. Ideally the film seemed and sounded like the true story that has inspired it. Even the family setting welcoming the cabin crew in the old woman's home, the sights of her cooking, the thoughtful hand-woven gift all connect with the viewers straight to their heart. It all seems too known, too comfortable, too nostalgic. The hesitation of the cabin crew while accepting the invitation, her communication with the grandmother in spite of language and cultural differences, the warm hug while parting all suggested the girl has found another home across the globe.

The Innovative Idea and Brand Management through Social Connect:

For British Airways, India is their second largest market outside U.K. owing to the large number of Indians residing there who visit India or has families visiting them from India. So, for British Airways, this campaign was a wonderful instrument to strategically place their brand as "Caring" and "Friendly" in the minds of Indians in the context of the cold treatment they often receive from other airlines. This is not essentially old school advertising with lofty ideals and path breaking things, but branded content with a good story and excellent execution. And characteristically so, they used all the in-flight amenities offered by British Airways beautifully in the film- from comfortable seats to choices in own languages and obviously their loving care of customers with individual attention. And that proves the world of communication is moving toward the avenues of branded content.

The campaign was criticized by experts of being too long and losing out viewers and problem of segmented communication to a specific audience. The potential does exist for many stories to be told in the travel companion, travelogue, and bank of travel stories. British Airways presented their human face through the air hostess who made an effort to know a place (India) by connecting with its people. The Indian family culture, strong bond, acceptance of one and all and a soothing sensation laced with love and care made the airhostess realize the true essence of life. The campaign gave the viewers a sense of being more nuanced, modest and believable and put their trust on British Airways. It has given them an edge over their competitors by adopting the more accepted way of storytelling to Indians and winning a permanent place by connecting emotionally.

Research Limitations/ Implications: The conclusions and projections are based on the authors' interpretation of the cases as they have occurred. The paper consists of the marketing campaigns by various companies which are thought to be acting as influencer in the minds of the Indian people. Many such more can be evaluated by future researchers since the field is dynamic.

Practical Implications: Professionals and students engaged with the marketing, advertisement, and strategic brand management arena, and in related areas can appreciate the growing importance of such innovative marketing campaigns through this paper. In today's dynamic world, marketers must think about long term sustainability which is helped through presenting their companies in a "different" way. With the technological innovations, it is easier to cater to a much broader section of people and influencing them in a positive manner.

Social Implications: The innovative marketing campaigns ensures two-way communication between the company and target audience. The feedback from them paves the way for increasing trust and mutual dependency between the two sides. The best way for business sustainability in the long run is through nurturing this precious relationship. This paper tries to focus on the societal implications and the relationship goals the companies and marketers achieved by strategically engaging their brands in these innovative marketing campaigns.

Analysis & Conclusion:

Marketing in a Volatile, Uncertain, Complex and Ambiguous environment is difficult, but the need of the hour is sustainable techniques in marketing. Short term profits and objectives should be traded off with long term goals and customer relationship. Marketing should focus on providing benefit to the customers and addressing the problems faced by the customers, only then will we have a stable society where business can thrive. The cases stated show how these companies have been able to brand the products & services and build a relationship with their customers by providing value to them. The goal of all the companies should be betterment of the society and this would ultimately lead to survival of the brand and long-term profits.

Today marketing campaigns have become an important tool for communication playing a role changer in consumer buying behavior. Interestingly, today's new hero is Emotional Appeal via Social Advertising campaigns – the brands have shifted from rational to emotional approaches slowly but steadily. Though these campaigns do not

directly convert to sales, the marketers are using this more to connect directly to the Indian consumers through their minds. It affects and influences consumer behavior directly and indirectly through positive brand recall and brand attitude. According to a report by Nielsen, these innovative social marketing campaigns create a lingering effect in the minds of the consumers and ultimately increase sales. This new breed of marketing campaigns tries to achieve exactly that—a positively rated brand by Indian consumers perceived emotionally! Marketers are doing their brand management strategically to deliver this.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Ajzen I, Fishbein M. Understanding attitudes and predicting social behavior. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall; 1980
- [2]. Andreasen, A.R.(1994),“Social marketing: Its definition and domain”, Journal of Public Policy & Marketing,13(1), 108-14.
- [3]. Andreasen, A.R.(1997),“From ghetto marketing to social marketing: bringing social relevance to mainstream marketing”, Journal of Public Policy & Marketing, 16(1),129-131.
- [4]. Andreasen, A.R.(2002).“Marketing Social Marketing in the Social Change Marketplace”, Journal of Public Policy & Marketing, 21(1), 3-13.
- [5]. Batra et al. (1986). “Affective Responses Mediating Acceptance of Advertising”, Journal of Consumer Research, 13 (September), 234-239.
- [6]. Belch GE, Belch MA (1998). Advertising and Promotion. New York: McGraw- Hill.
- [7]. Berger, J. and E. M. Schwartz (2011). “What drives immediate and ongoing word of mouth?” Journal of Marketing Research, 48(5),869-880.
- [8]. Khan, R. and Sindhu, S. (2015). “An Investigation of Advertising Appeal on Consumer Response in Service Advertising”, Management Studies and Economic Systems (MSES), 2 (1), 39-505.
- [9]. Kotler et al. (2002). “Social Marketing”, Sage Publications.
- [10]. Kotler, P. and Zaltman, G. (1971). “Social Marketing: An Approach to Planned Social Change”, Journal of Marketing, 35(3) ,3-12
- [11]. Lenon, R. et al. (2010). “Social marketing and distracted driving Behaviors among young adults: The effectiveness of fear appeals”, Academy of Marketing Studies Journal, 14(2) , 95-113.
- [12]. Mohsen, S. et al (2015). “Investigating the effect of rational and emotional advertising appeals of HamraheAval mobile operator on attitude towards advertising and brand attitude (case study: student users of mobile in the area of Tehran)”, International Journal of Asian Social Science, 5(4), 233-244.
- [13]. Saad, F. (2011). “Brand Loyalty Through Emotional Advertising”, Journal Of Marketing, Philosophy and Practice, 1(1), 10-13.
- [14]. Sofi, S.A. and Nika, F.A. (2013).“Impact of Subliminal Messages in TV Advertisement on customer behavior (A Case Study of Youth in Kashmir Province of J&K)”,Journal of Business Management & Social Sciences (JBM&SSR), 2(12), 12-28.
- [15]. Stankovic, L. (2006). “Strategic Brand Management in Global Environment”, Economics & Organisation, FACTA UNIVERSITATIS 3(2), 125-133.
- [16]. Strebinger, A. (2004). “Strategic Brand Concept and Brand Architecture Strategyba Proposed Model”, Advances in Consumer Research,31, 656-661.
- [17]. Veljkovic, S and Kalicanin, D. (2016). “Improving business performance through Brand Management practice”, Economic Analysis, L11(208), 137-167.
- [18]. Verhellen, Y. (2013). “Consumer Response to Brands placed in Youtube Movies: The Effect of Prominence and Endorser Expertise”, Journal of Electronic Commerce Research, 14(4), 287-303.
- [19]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oYyKA8wp844>; retrieved on 25/12/2021
- [20]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9bH1mvhFYUI>; retrieved on 29/12/2021
- [21]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Wdaf2PVdg0o>; retrieved on 31/1/2022
- [22]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=I5ZXB3Jxsmo>; retrieved on 8/2/2022
- [23]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=827gusjTYbo>; retrieved on 8/2/2022